

Advocating for the Role of Library and Information Specialists in Evidence-Based Toxicology

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Abstract

The judicious use of high-quality evidence in decision-making and policy formation is an essential practice across disciplines. Organizations such as the Cochrane Collaboration, JBI, the Campbell Collaboration, and the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence have made it their primary mission to promote the creation and application of trusted evidence to improve individual health outcomes and public health. These organizations focus on evidence synthesis, which has become a cornerstone of multidisciplinary evidence-based practice. Keeping pace with, making sense of, and organizing relevant evidence can present challenges to researchers, which is why these organizations have long advocated for the expertise of library and information specialists (LIS) in evidence-based work. LIS possess exceptional proficiency to support evidence synthesis workflows, such as constructing sensitive, reproducible searches, providing methodological guidance, and supporting the use of numerous research tools and software. LIS also maintain skills in other important areas, such as information and data management, writing and publishing, research impact, evolving technologies, and more. We propose that LIS are valuable contributors to evidence-based toxicology.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
EBT	Evidence-Based Toxicology
EPA	U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
ES	Evidence Synthesis
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
IACUC	Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees
KCC	Key Characteristics of Carcinogens
KE	Key Events
LIS	Library and Information Specialists
LLM	Large Language Model
SR	Systematic Review

Introduction: Embracing Evidence

Evidence-based toxicology has its origins in evidence-based medicine, which necessitates applying evidence from published studies to challenges faced in the clinic. In 1991, in an editorial called "Evidence-Based Medicine", Gordon Guyatt proposed a fictional, but not unrealistic, scenario whereby an internist was faced with the task of following a clinical protocol to treat a patient. She realized that she did not understand the diagnostic properties of the tests she had ordered, and subsequently turned to

searching in MEDLINE, which is today contained within PubMed, the National Library of Medicine's bibliographic literature database (Guyatt, 1991). With the help of a librarian, she retrieved a study that aided her in making a clinical decision to manage the care of the patient (Guyatt, 1991). Rather than looking to past experiences or seeking anecdotal input, it becomes essential to incorporate "additional strategies, including quickly tracking down publications of studies that are directly relevant to the . . . problem, critically appraising these studies, and applying the results of the best studies to the . . . problem at hand" (Guyatt, 1991). Building these foundational strategies, wrote Guyatt, "[requires] skills of literature retrieval, critical appraisal, and information synthesis" (Guyatt, 1991). Indeed, research has demonstrated that decision-making techniques often lack scientific rigor due to lack of time. Covell et al. (1985) conducted an interview study with 47 clinicians and found that although the overwhelming majority ranked finding and integrating information into their practice as important, they admitted that they lacked comprehensive knowledge of appropriate resources and were often overwhelmed by the volume of information and the task of searching for articles. A subsequent review of the literature found that "time" persists as the biggest barrier to information seeking, followed by challenges with technology, limited database searching skills, cost, and the assumption that reviewing new evidence would not change care (Davies, 2007). In 1996, Guyatt's own mentor, Dr. David Sackett, defined evidence-based medicine as "the conscientious, explicit and judicious use of current best evidence in making decisions" (Sackett et al., 1996), perhaps with the unwritten implication that current decision-making techniques were "less than scientific" (Sur & Dahm, 2011).

The systematic synthesis of evidence has become integral to implementing the use of higher quality evidence in science. Archie Cochrane, an epidemiological researcher, proponent of evidence-based medicine, and student of Bradford Hill, called for randomized controlled trials to measure the effectiveness of healthcare interventions in the 1970s (Chalmers, 2008). With multiple randomized controlled trials addressing the same topic, there was a need to be able to collate, compare, and synthesize results. Cochrane's call marked the emergence of more comprehensive literature reviews of existing evidence. These reviews were intended to minimize bias by using prespecified

eligibility criteria for selecting information through rigorous, methodical, and systematic approaches. Systematic and scoping reviews gained tremendous momentum and prestige from the evidence synthesis (ES) movement and were considered among the "highest" forms of evidence for clinical decision-making for many years. Iterations of the evidence-based medicine pyramid have placed systematic reviews of randomized controlled trials at or near the top of the hierarchy for over two decades (Guyatt et al., 1995), although more recently these hierarchies have been under scrutiny for underestimating study quality over a preference for study design (Deshmukh et al., 2025; Murad et al., 2016).

In the 21st century, toxicologists began to adopt ES to encourage objective, data-driven decisions in risk assessments and safety standards. The phrase "evidence-based toxicology" (EBT) made its debut to the world in a conference keynote in 2005, after researchers recognized a need for unbiased and transparent approaches in the synthesis of toxicological evidence (Hartung & Tsaioun, 2024). Hartung and Hoffman pointed out the similarities of information overload between clinical medicine and toxicology, drew parallels between clinical diagnosis and exposure assessment, and advocated for meta-analysis and structured review to achieve EBT (Hoffmann & Hartung, 2006). Hartung subsequently established nine considerations for EBT with a focus on scientific rigor and transparency to overcome the complex challenges faced by toxicologists in their work (Hartung, 2009).

The foundational principle of the judicious use of evidence is being able to effectively find and assess literature. Library and information specialists (LIS) have been involved in teaching evidence-based approaches to students, professionals, and faculty since the 1990s and conducting searches and supporting researchers' reference requests for evidence for decades prior, in ways similar to Guyatt's scenario (Guyatt, 1991). Unfortunately, of late, ES reviews have been facing credibility challenges due to lack of adherence to rigorous standards, including literature searching.

Evidence Synthesis: Hazards Abound

The popularity of ES has resulted in an explosion of published systematic reviews (SRs) and related review types (e.g. scoping, umbrella, realist, concept analyses, evidence gap maps, systematic evidence maps, etc.). In its fifty-plus years of existence, the art and science of ES has had impact and value in a variety of disciplines besides clinical medicine and toxicology, including education and the social sciences; it continues to expand to other fields such as computer science (Campbell Collaboration, n.d.; Götz, 2018; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020). Pertinent to the field of toxicology, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the United States Food & Drug Administration (FDA) established their support of systematic review as an appropriate methodology for risk evaluation and risk assessment (Environmental Protection Agency (U.S.), 2018; Food and Drug Administration (U.S.), 2025; National Research Council, 2014). Due to the complexities of finding all available evidence, major evidence-focused organizations have in the last 15 years added directives to their manuals advocating for LIS involvement in the literature search and methods (Campbell Collaboration, n.d.; Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2022; JBI, 2024; Lefebvre et al., 2019). ES is a true team science, and it is one that demands time and skill in order to produce high quality and reliable outcomes.

It certainly seems as though ES is here to stay; however, toxicologists may agree that it is the dose that makes the poison, and in the case of ES, the injection of low-quality reviews into the published literature is creating adverse effects in science. Ioannidis proposed that a "large majority of produced systematic reviews and meta-analyses are unnecessary, misleading, and/or conflicted," writing that many published reviews were redundant. He called for major reforms to review standards and quality (Ioannidis, 2016). One author group found the equivalent of 80 systematic reviews being published per day with a high amount of topical overlap resulting in research waste (Hoffmann et al., 2021). Another group called evidence synthesis a "Pandora's Box", noting a "plethora of overlapping evidence synthesis approaches and duplicate, redundant, and poor-quality reviews" (Munn et al., 2023). In 2019, Wallach questioned the purpose, quality, and credibility of "most reviews" due to the nearly exponential increase in publication rates and their failing (or complete lack of) methods, citing a "meta-analysis

metastasis" (Wallach, 2019), further contributing to integrity and trustworthiness challenges in the domain.

Beyond rigorous and systematic approaches, a critical component of ES is that of a reproducible methodology. This requires transparency when describing methods used, including the literature search component, since the literature search is foundational to the process. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA), first published in 2009 and subsequently comprehensively updated in 2020, is a 27-item checklist used for the reporting of ES reviews (Moher et al., 2010; Page et al., 2021). Fifteen PRISMA extensions cover additional aspects of reporting in elements of ES protocols, abstracts, harms, and more (PRISMA Executive, 2020). Among them, PRISMA-Search (PRISMA-S) is a discipline-agnostic extension of the original PRISMA Statement focused on best practices for reporting literature searches (Page et al., 2021). It contains 16 reporting items that provide more detailed guidance than the PRISMA 2020 alone (Rethlefsen et al., 2021).

Librarians and Evidence Synthesis: An Antidote to the Chaos

The roles of LIS in supporting ES work has become considered so essential across research organizations and institutions that in many cases it is being provisioned as a service, sometimes even fee-based (Demetres et al., 2023; Kallaher et al., 2020; Lackey et al., 2019; McKeown & Ross-White, 2019). There has also been a rise in LIS co-authorship for this work, largely based on the recognition of the contributions that LIS make to ES (Aamodt et al., 2019; Bramer et al., 2018; Meert et al., 2016; Rethlefsen et al., 2015; Schellinger et al., 2021; Whitney et al., 2024). ES searches are fundamental to ES reviews, establishing the data that will be selected for synthesis and analysis. These searches take significant effort to do well (Erwin, 2004; Hausner et al., 2012; Rethlefsen et al., 2015; Rethlefsen et al., 2021). Creating a search strategy for any type of ES requires knowledge of available information sources, including databases and grey literature, plus the ability to effectively use those information sources. LIS often possess the deep and practiced knowledge of these bibliographic literature databases that enables us to conduct sensitive and comprehensive searches in much less time

than researchers whose expertise does not focus on finding information. LIS participation in ES helps to increase reproducibility, search sensitivity, comprehensiveness, improve transparency of manuscripts and reports, and reduce unintentional omissions of relevant evidence (Rethlefsen et al., 2015). Systematic searches are dependent on the user's knowledge of the behavior of syntax, translation, subject headings, field tags, subheadings, technological idiosyncrasies, user interfaces, and system updates. Search results need to be organized through a deduplication process and processed into files that are compatible with different tools. When possible, LIS also provide peer reviews of each others' searches to help improve search sensitivity and reduce errors (Blackwood, 2015; McGinnis, 2025; McGowan et al., 2016; Relevo & Paynter, 2012). "Systematic reviews need systematic searchers," wrote McGowan and Sampson (2005), and we agree.

Toxicologists working in ES often find themselves in the difficult position of having to incorporate and synthesize multiple streams of evidence from human, animal, and cell studies (Hartung & Tsaion, 2024). There is also the imperative to rely heavily on published peer reviewed data, but to acknowledge and incorporate other data as well. Particularly important in toxicology research is the idea that evidence of absence does not mean absence of evidence (Wandall et al., 2007), and that while a comprehensive literature search may be representative of existing published literature, the findings may still "deviate from what it would have been if all conducted studies had been published" (Wandall et al., 2007). Grey literature should not be overlooked in environmental health and regulatory science, and could include authoritative, government, regulatory, laboratory, pharmaceutical, or other publications that are difficult to find and obtain but should be considered for eligibility and synthesis (Ford et al., 2016; Scott et al., 2025). LIS are proficient in searching grey literature and documenting those searches. To overcome and assist challenges faced by researchers, LIS have established methods for dealing with multiple streams of evidence, grey literature, reproducible literature search documentation, and search updates.

LIS participation does not stop when information searches are complete. LIS have established competencies and roles related to contributions to ES (Spencer & Eldredge,

2018; Townsend et al., 2017), outlining not only our support of the literature searches, but also support of question and protocol development, writing, training, review-type selection, tool selection, and more. Ever present are artificial intelligence (AI) tools that mine and visualize bodies of literature (e.g. Elicit, ResearchRabbit, Connected Papers, Perplexity, etc.). In many cases, LIS are able not only to offer training and guidance for the responsible use of these multitudinous tools, but also provision enterprise licensing, accounts, and access.

As LIS, we are all too aware that SR searches are often not reported well or at all, not reproducible when reported, and frequently contain errors that can impact the recall of the search (Koffel, 2015; McGowan & Sampson, 2005; Rethlefsen et al., 2024; Rethlefsen et al., 2015; Salvador-Oliván et al., 2019). Because LIS also partner in co-authoring manuscript methods and results, they can ensure that all necessary PRISMA-S items are appropriately reported and that searches are reproducible. Without LIS partnership, for example, many times authors may confuse guidelines for reporting with guidelines for methodology. One need not search very extensively in PubMed for a recently published SR that claims it was "conducted" instead of "reported" according to PRISMA, but the statement and its extensions provide very little direction as to the SR's methodological conduct, instead asking authors to clearly and transparently describe their study. There are also many recently published SRs providing merely a list of search terms but no detail as to how they were combined, being therefore irreproducible. In fact, in our study of a sample of 100 systematic review searches, we found that only one was actually reproducible, which entailed that all of the conducted database searches met six key PRISMA-S reporting criteria and that there was less than 10% deviation between the original search and the reproduction (Rethlefsen et al., 2024; Rethlefsen et al., 2021). We found, as have other researchers, that involving LIS as co-authors in ES improves reporting quality (Aamodt et al., 2019; Rethlefsen et al., 2024; Rethlefsen et al., 2015; Schellinger et al., 2021).

Over the past decade, LIS have sought other ways to improve the published body of ES literature, particularly by participating as peer reviewers at journals that recognize their special expertise. We recently examined the utility, impact, and perspectives of LIS as

methodological peer reviewers for BMJ Group journals (Rethlefsen et al., 2024; Rethlefsen et al., 2025). We found that LIS can be willing and valuable methodological peer reviewers for ES manuscripts. LIS often felt that they had a real impact upon both the editors' decisions and the authors' subsequent revisions (Rethlefsen et al., 2025). We believe LIS are an underutilized peer reviewing resource that may help editors improve the quality of SRs that make it to publication (Grossetta Nardini et al., 2019; Ibragimova & Fulbright, 2024; Rethlefsen et al., 2025).

Librarians in Toxicology: A Synergistic Effect

In recent times, the field of toxicology has experienced a major shift in policies to "foster development and use of new tests" (Krewski et al., 2010) to move away from animal testing in chemical risk assessment. This evolution has birthed ideas like the three Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement), New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), and Next Generation Risk Assessments (NGRAs). In their book chapter in *Finding Your Seat at the Table* called, "Librarians and the IACUC," librarians Ratajeski and Miller identified LIS as an asset to Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees (IACUC) and the like with three major areas of contribution: doing literature searches, reviewing literature searches for the committee or principle investigator, and providing instruction to those involved in alternatives to animal research. LIS sometimes have specialized training in supporting their local IACUC and searching for animal alternatives to satisfy the requirements of existing standards to meet the mandates of the Animal Welfare Act and U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) Policy for the treatment of experimental animals (Ratajeski & Miller, 2022). Literature searching for animal alternatives can help avoid duplication in such experiments, identify alternative, less complex animal models, and improve the well-being of experimental animals (University of North Carolina, 2025). LIS have also been involved in formulating literature searches around the International Agency for Research on Cancer's (IARC) "Key Characteristics of Carcinogens" (KCCs), an integral part of cancer risk evaluations and hazard assessments (Barupal et al., 2021; Guyton et al., 2018; Smith, 2019; Smith et al., 2015), while scientists have been making an effort to integrate KCCs in more systematic ways (Wikoff et al., 2019). A recent poster presentation highly recommended collaboration

with LIS in the development of protocols for identifying adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) and key events (KEs) (Viviani et al., 2025).

Many LIS have skills in digital curation and preservation, as evidenced by their involvement in institutional and open data repositories (Allard et al., 2005). Other LIS support potential authors with journal selection recommendations and tips for measuring research impact (Sarli et al., 2010; Spencer & Eldredge, 2018). Regarding data, LIS have championed the FAIR data principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, further supporting transparency and reproducibility in research (Wilkinson et al., 2016). In 2025, information professionals from around the world volunteered efforts to capture and document deprecated, at-risk, and disappearing U.S. government data (Data Rescue Project, 2025b). Since February 2025, the Data Rescue Project volunteers have archived over 1,713 datasets across 90 United States government offices, including relied-upon toxicological resources such as CompTox, EJScreen, and other EPA data (Data Rescue Project, 2025a).

Finally, the last several years have seen an increase in the involvement of LIS in the ethical use of AI and Large-Language Models (LLMs), advocating for transparency and integrity while simultaneously working to build digital and health literacy skills en masse (Flemyng et al., 2025; Resnik & Hosseini, 2025; Zerilli et al., 2022) through curriculum, training, and general advocacy. The Responsible Use of AI in Evidence Synthesis (RAISE) recommendations, which has several LIS on the author panel, provide guidance on selecting and assessing AI tools for responsible use in ES, as well as disclosing how AI was used (Flemyng et al., 2025; Thomas et al., 2025).

Conclusion: Preventing Adverse Effects in Information Overdose

LIS play a critical and increasingly strategic role in supporting researchers in evidence-based approaches. Our expertise in systematic searching, information retrieval, and methodological reporting quality strengthens the rigor and reproducibility of EBT and ES. As evidence and its use continues to shape regulatory decision-making, risk and

safety assessments, and future research, the involvement of LIS in all stages of the research process is essential. LIS can support researchers in many other tasks that fall along the research lifecycle. Recognizing LIS as true team collaborators enhances the quality of ES in toxicology and ensures that scientific conclusions and decision-making are grounded in unbiased, systematic methods and well-documented bodies of evidence.

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